

Pepper Leaf Disease Detection using Image Processing

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Abstract— The major crisis facing by agricultural industry is plant disease. Plant diseases lead to the poor yield and thus results in economic loss. Constant monitoring over plants should be done to minimize diseases and destruction of our farm. The major cash crop in our state are Pepper, Cardamom, Cashew etc. Diseases such as, Leaf spot, Mosaic virus, Verticillium wilt, Blight, etc. Determination of these diseases can be done by monitoring the plant and process it via a Machine Learning technique called Image Processing. Image Processing factorize the images and returns the disease and its remedies if defected. This leaf disease detection system will help farmers in taking necessary precautions. For implementing the framework tools and modules like Kaggle Notebook, Tensorflow, and Keras used. The proposed model aims in reducing complexity in classifying apple leaf disease using deep learning. The proposed system shows the best validation accuracy of 93.3% on the pepper leaf disease dataset.

Keywords—*image processing, machine learning, leaf disease detection system*

I. INTRODUCTION

There was a time majority of the people got busy in farming. But agriculture and farming are treated as a “waste of time” in the modern era. The major reason behind this is plant disease and natural calamities. Natural calamities can be considered as a out of our box content whereas plant diseases can be determined and needed precautions can be took for the better tomorrow. Here we are considering the case of Pepper plants. Most of the pepper plant disease can be detected by checking the plant leaves. Usually seen diseases are Verticillium wilt, Damping off disease, Leaf spot, Mosaic virus etc. Manually analysing and detecting will take time and is a difficult task.

A machine learning algorithm is used to analyse the leaf and detect whether the leaf is defected or not and if defected, it determines which is the disease. Further remedies will also be provided as part of the output. In classical patterns, tedious tasks such as image processing, feature extraction, and feature classification are now simplified by deep learning. The effects of picture recognition improve. Deep learning has significantly lowered the time and effort required to detect objects. It also aids in real-time decision-making and saves agricultural losses. Our paper focuses on disease detection in the leaf and encourages farmers and

producers to be more disease-aware. CNN was used to create our model. It's a conventional deep learning model. This approach can extract features from the source image automatically in the case of disease detection. CNN simplifies the recognition problem and saves time because it is an end-to-end structure.

The model can be implemented on a Farming sector and can easily monitor pepper plants there. The system collects and check the matches with the training data to detect if defected. The final output is disease with remedies if defected.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Midhun P Mathew, Et al [1] propose the idea of detecting diseases on Apple leaves using Machine Learning technique. Plant disease is the major reason behind agriculture failure. Computer vision and deep learning advancements are assisting in resolving the issues. In addition, it gives highly accurate findings in a real-time setting. When compared to other models, Yolo can detect more accurate findings in disease detection. As a result, the concept of deep learning benefits modern farming.

Abirami Devaraj, Et al [2] propose the concept of tracing the defect of the plant by observing the image of the plant leaf. Illness detection is accomplished by steps such as image loading, pre-processing, segmentation, extraction, and classification. The images of leaves are used to diagnose plant illnesses. As a result, image processing techniques can be used to discover and classify diseases in agricultural applications.

Surampalli Ashok, Et al [3] has come with the idea of early detection of diseases that occurs on Tomato Plant Leaf. This paper proposes to identify the Tomato Plant Leaf disease using image processing techniques based on Image segmentation, clustering, and open-source algorithms, thus all contributing to a reliable, safe, and accurate system of leaf disease with the specialization to Tomato Plants.

R Anand, Et al [4] The research proposes combining image processing and artificial neural approaches to diagnose the pathology of the brinjal leaf. In this study, the K-means clustering algorithm for segmentation and the Neural-network for classification were used to detect brinjal leaf disease. The proposed detection model, which is based on artificial neural networks, is highly good at detecting leaf illnesses.

Ch. Usha Kumari, Et al [5] The suggested system's goal is to use image processing techniques to identify the leaf spot. The illness identification process in this study is broken down into four stages: picture acquisition, image segmentation, feature extraction, and classification. The K-means clustering approach is used for picture segmentation, and features are generated from the disease-affected cluster. The neural network (NN) classifier was employed in this study.

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to detect whether the plant is defected or not. The main advantage of this is, it will return us the disease and the remedies for the detected disease. Primarily we train our system various diseases that can happen to a Pepper plant. The test and train data consists of various images of Pepper leaf diseases. The model should be able to correctly classify the diseases.

Fig 1: Proposed Methodology

A. Data Collection

The project's data set availability was a big problem that we experienced while working on it. Because there are just a few public data sets relating to illnesses in plant leaves, developments in this field of agriculture are not readily apparent. The data set dubbed plant village, which is available in Kaggle, is used for the majority of agricultural studies. We're looking at the Pepper Leaf Diseases data set. There are 2500 photos in the data collection, which are divided into four categories. Table 1 lists the various classes. Each image features a single leaf set on a solid

background. Infected locations are shown by bounding boxes.

Class Number	Class Name
0	Verticillium wilt
1	Blight
2	Leaf spot
3	Mosaic virus

i. Verticillium wilt

Fig 2 : Verticillium wilt

Verticillium wilt is a bacteria causing illness. Bacterial wilt can be considered as a serious disease that can be seen in pepper plants as well as in many vegetables. The plants infected with this disease will begin to wither starting from one side.

ii. Blight

Fig 3 : Blight

Blight can be alternatively called Phytothora. This can be identified by a slight wilting with yellowishness over the leaves. This disease is caused by climate change, soil, water problem.

iii. Leaf spot

Fig 4 : Leaf spot

Leaf spot is a bacterial infection that is commonly seen on pepper leaves. This is mostly spread during rainy, humid and warm conditions. Touching or wetting the leaves will promote spreading this to other leaves.

iv. Mosaic virus

Fig 5 : Mosaic virus

Mosaic virus as its name indicates, it is a virus causing illness. This is spread by insects like aphids. This disease can also be spread when plants come in contact. This will become problematic during dry weather

B. Procedure

The term "object detection" or "identification" refers to a computer vision or image processing technology. It is mostly employed in the security and surveillance fields. In this case, the CNN algorithm is used to detect plant illnesses in the data set. Primarily we accept an input image from the user and then when we proceed to the next step the computer will decompose the image and convert it into system acceptable format. The data we had used to train the system will go for a matching with the input image and the most matching profile will be retrieved as the output. The output will be in the form, the input image with healthy or defected tag, if defected it will retrieve the name of disease and its remedies.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a method for detecting diseases on Pepper leaves using Convolutional Neural Network. It provides a good accuracy for detecting pepper leaf disease via Machine Learning. Here primarily we teach the system about various diseases that could happen to a pepper plant. The dataset contains test and train data of pepper leaves in which healthy and categorised defected leaves are present. Then the system accepts the image as input and checks for the possible match among healthy and defected leaves. The data with the highest match will be considered as its state and returns the corresponding data. Also, real time pepper leaf disease detection in videos can be done in future. The other scope is that the system could predict which plant would be more disease prompt based on its current status.

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